

A scrapbook of child stories as a media to improving the story-telling skill

Fetty Fellasufah¹, Ali Mustadi²

¹Elementary Education Postgraduate, Yogyakarta State University, Indonesia

²Department of Elementary Education, Yogyakarta State University, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Sep 17, 2020

Revised Apr 11, 2021

Accepted May 7, 2021

Keywords:

Children story
Elementary school
Scrapbook
Skills of storytelling

ABSTRACT

This research aimed to determine the effect of scrapbook child stories as a media for storytelling skills for elementary school students. This type of research was a quasi-experimental quantitative study with a pretest-posttest group design. The population of this research was second grade elementary school students of Candimulyo sub-district, involving two classes as the control class and the experimental class. The test results were then analyzed using the prerequisite test and hypothesis testing. The prerequisite test consists of the normality test using the Kolmogorov Smirnov test and the homogeneity test using the One Way Anova. Hypothesis testing using t-test with independent sample t-test. The results of the analysis were then tested using a significance level of 0.05. The results of this result showed that the control class and the experimental class had a normal and homogeneous distribution. The t-test results showed a significance level <0.05. It means that there was a significant effect of scrapbook child stories to improve storytelling skills.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Fetty Fellasufah
Elementary Education Postgraduate
Yogyakarta State University
01 Colombo Road, Yogyakarta Township 55281, Indonesia
Email: fettyfellasufah.2017@student.uny.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

Language skills are one of the aspects related to the success of learning, although many consider this easy, in fact this ability is still lagging behind other countries. As much 13.11% of Indonesian residents are more than 10 years old who read newspapers or magazines, the rest prefer watching television [1]. Lack of reading activity will result in a lack of language knowledge and skills.

Some language skills that are important for elementary school students to master are writing and speaking skills [2]. Learning to speak is a big concern in the world of education. Speaking skills are categorized as good if the listener can know and understand the meaning of the message conveyed by the speaker [3]. Planting concepts in speaking will continue to be used continuously, from children even to the end of life. Therefore, it requires perseverance and accuracy in learning to speak for children, especially school age children.

One of the activities that can be used in an effort to improve speaking skills is storytelling [4]. Through storytelling, students will verbalize about the experiences they have had. Both the experiences they get themselves and those they get from other sources. Storytelling also involves cognitive, mental, and knowledge processes to exchange information. Storytelling is considered as a verbal communication activity carried out by the storyteller to the listener [5]-[7]. What is conveyed is in the form of a story, experience, or

the story of an incident by way of delivery using voice, movement, and media to support the course of the story. Storytelling has a purpose for a variety of knowledge, fostering imagination, and communication [8]-[10]. Storytelling fosters the ability to understand the cause and effect of a story so that it can be used as a method in learning activities. Thus, children's insight and imagination will increase. In addition, telling stories is closely related to the world of children, so that it will be easier to improve speaking skills. In addition, storytelling can be used as a way to develop children's language skills as well as a way to increase their motivation in learning [11].

Skills development in students will certainly be more effective when using learning tools or better known as media. Through the use of media, it is hoped that students will be more motivated in their learning activities. The teacher as a facilitator is expected to be able to develop learning media [12]. The use of media in learning can increase learning activities, make it easier for students to learn and have a positive impact on students' abilities [13], [14].

The development of children's story media in accordance with the characteristics of elementary school students will be developed through this research. The media is a scrapbook of child stories. Scrapbook [15] is a book that contains photos or images that are arranged creatively with words that describe the atmosphere in the photo. The use of media in storytelling activities can be increased from the belief, mastery of story content, and the ability to express themselves [16]. Image media can be used to introduce new vocabulary to students, thereby ensuring students gain understanding of storytelling activities [11]. The scrapbook contains an arrangement of pictures that can make it easier for students to make stories. Through pictures and keywords, it can help students in storytelling activities [17].

Based on the results of preliminary studies conducted through observation, interview, and questionnaire, several problems were found related to students' storytelling skills. For example the students telling stories are not clear with their soft voices. Storytelling activities haven't a good attitude, because students tell stories with their heads down or use the books to cover their faces. In addition, storytelling learning takes a long time and students haven't shown enthusiasm to listen to the stories from their friends. Various things found in the preliminary study and this study aims to determine the effect scrapbook of child stories for storytelling skills of grade II elementary school students.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This was quantitative research involving the control class and the experimental class. Research subjects in the study were divided into the control class and the experimental class. The control class consisted of 23 students and the experimental class with 20 students. The design of this research uses the design form Pretest-Posttest Control Group Design [18]. The operational trials used a quasi experiment method with a non-equivalent comparison-group design [19]. The operational trial design can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The design research

The resulting data in development research is quantitative data. The data collection instrument in this study was used to collect data from each stage of the research. The instrument used is in the form of performance questions. Techniques are related to the methods or methods used in the data collection process. The data collection technique used in the study was a test.

The intended test result is a test of student performance through storytelling practice. Through storytelling, students can tell a story, experience, or story of an incident using sound, movement, and media to support the storyline. Using scrapbooks of child stories becomes a medium when students want to tell stories that have been made orally. In the assessment of storytelling skills, success indicators have been summarized including: 1) the suitability of the story content, 2) storytelling expression, 3) vocal storytelling, 4) story telling fluency, 5) eye contact, 6) pauses and 7) accuracy of story meaning [20], [4], [21].

The data analysis technique for students' storytelling skills used the t-test. Before knowing the effect scrapbook of child stories for the students' storytelling skill, first the data in the control class and the experimental class must meet the prerequisite test. The prerequisite test was carried out by means of the normality test and the homogeneity test.

The normality test is carried out to test whether the distribution of data is normally distributed or not, so the Kolmogorov Smirnov one-sample test is used. Obtaining test results provided that the sample data is normally distributed if the significance is > 0.05 . However, if the significance < 0.05 , the sample data is not normally distributed. The homogeneity test was conducted to determine whether or not the sample was randomly selected from the population so that the One Way ANOVA test was used. The sample data is homogeneous if the significance value is > 0.05 . Conversely, if the significance < 0.05 , the data is not homogeneous.

After testing the normality and homogeneity tests, then an independent t-test is carried out using the independent sample t-test. The reference value of significance used is if > 0.05 then the hypothesis is accepted. In more detail, here are the research hypotheses used in this study.

Ha : There is a significant effect on storytelling skills between students who take lessons using scrapbook of child stories media and those who don't take lessons using scrapbook of child stories media.

Ho : There is no significant effect on storytelling skills between students who take part in learning using scrapbook of child stories media and those who do not participate in learning using scrapbook of child stories media.

The criteria for decision making for acceptance and rejection of Ho used a significance level of 0.05. If the significance value > 0.05 then Ho is accepted, but if the significance value < 0.05 then Ho is rejected.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The scrapbook of child stories contains Indonesian language teaching materials especially story writing and storytelling materials for grade II students of elementary school. The scrapbook of child stories referred to the teaching objectives, Curriculum 2013, standard of competence, core competence, basic competence, indicators of learning, and teaching materials. The innovation developed by adjusting the components and learning objectives. Arranging the content according with the objectives will have a good effect [22]. The scrapbook of child stories consists of several parts, including the introductory part, content part, final part, and closing part. Consist of the scrapbook based on the literature study conducted. Scrapbook child stories a media for learning storytelling referring to concept of innovation, functioning of the innovation, its benefits, and its meaning [23]. The learning materials are presented with illustration and pictures interesting to creating learning activity enthusiastic for students. The Figure 2 are the cover design and material contained on scrapbook of child stories. The title used is an adjustment to the learning theme and goal as well as the material presented. In the Figure 3, there are some pictures of learning activities carried out using scrapbook of child stories.

Figure 2. Design scrapbook of child stories

Figure 3. Learning activities with scrapbook of child stories

The data obtained in this study were the results of the storytelling skills test aimed at grade II students. The test is carried out in two stages, namely pretest and posttest. Pretest is given to students before students get treatment, while posttest is given after students carry out the learning using scrapbooks of child stories media. The research data was taken to determine the differences in the control class and the experimental class. The control class is a class that follows learning without using scrapbook of child stories media, while the experimental class is a class that takes part in learning activities using scrapbook of child stories media. Table 1 displays the descriptive statistics of the control class and experimental class at the pretest stage.

Tabel 1. Pretest results

Group	N	Min.	Max.	\bar{X}
Control Class	23	50	80	66.30
Experimental Class	20	50	80	64

Table 1 shows the results of the student storytelling skills test which was carried out at the pretest stage. It is known that the control class with a total of 23 students got a minimum score of 50.00 and a maximum score of 80.00 with a class mean of 66.30. Whereas in the experimental class, which consisted of 20 students, the results obtained a minimum score of 50.00, a maximum score of 80.00, and a class average of 64.00. Table 2 displays the results of the storytelling skills test at the posttest stage.

Table 2. Posttest result

Score	Descriptives							
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Control	23	72.1739	9.74984	2.03298	67.9578	76.3901	55.00	90.00
Experiment	20	79.0000	7.53937	1.68585	75.4715	82.5285	65.00	90.00
Total	43	75.3488	9.34748	1.42548	72.4721	78.2256	55.00	90.00

Table 2 shows the results of the students' storytelling skills test which was carried out at the posttest stage. It is known that the control class with 23 students got a minimum score of 55.00 and a maximum score of 90.00 with a class average of 72.17. Meanwhile, in the experimental class, which consisted of 20 students, the results obtained a minimum score of 65.00, a maximum score of 90.00, and a class average of 79.00.

The increase in value can be seen from the results of the average value of students' storytelling skills at the pretest and posttest. In the control class, it is known that the average value of students' storytelling skills has increased from 66.30 to 72.17. Likewise, the experimental class experienced an increase from an average value of 64.00 to 79.00. Both classes showed an increase, but in the experimental class the difference in the increase in the average value showed a greater value, namely 15.00.

This explanation shows that the average score of the experimental class students' story skills is higher than the control class. So it can be seen that the results of students' storytelling skills have differences between students who take part in learning using scrapbook of child stories media and those who do not.

Data analysis was performed using hypothesis testing with t-test, but before that the prerequisite test was conducted first, namely the normality test and the homogeneity test. The normality test is carried out to test the distribution of data with normal distribution or not, so the Kolmogorov Smirnov one-sample test is used in the Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) 23.0 program. Obtaining test results provided that the sample data is normally distributed if the significance is > 0.05 . However, if the significance < 0.05 , the sample data is not normally distributed. The results of the normality test for storytelling skills for grade II students can be shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Test of normality

	Tests of Normality					
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Control	.145	16	.200*	.948	16	.459
Experiment	.166	16	.200*	.927	16	.218

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Based on the results of the normality test carried out, it can be seen that the data from the students' storytelling skills test has a normal distribution. This is evidenced by the significance value of each class, both the control class and the experimental class, which shows a number of $0.200 > 0.05$. Thus, it can be concluded that the data has a normal distribution.

Furthermore, the homogeneity test was carried out on the student test results. The homogeneity test was carried out to determine whether or not the sample was randomly selected from the population so that the One Way ANOVA test was used. The test is sought with the help of the SPSS 23.0 program. The sample data is homogeneous if the significance value is > 0.05 . Conversely, if the significance < 0.05 , the data is not homogeneous. The results of the class II storytelling skills homogeneity test can be shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Test of homogeneity of variances

Test of Homogeneity of Variances				
Score	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
	2.095	1	41	.155

Sourced from the table of the results of the homogeneity test of students' storytelling skills showed a significance value of 0.155. This value has a significance value > 0.05 , so it can be seen that the results of the storytelling skills posttest in operational trials are homogeneous data.

Based on the results of the calculation of the prerequisite test carried out, it was found that the data had a normal distribution with the variance of the two homogeneous class groups. Thus, then the hypothesis can be tested with the t-test. The hypothesis in this study is the effect of children's story scrapbooks on storytelling skills of grade II elementary school students.

Hypothesis testing in this study using independent sample t-test. The test is intended to determine whether there are differences in each dependent variable in the control class and the experimental class. The hypotheses in this study are

Ha : There is a significant effect on storytelling skills between students who take lessons using scrapbook of child stories media and those who don't learn using scrapbook of child stories media

Ho : There is no significant effect on storytelling skills between students who take lessons using scrapbook of child stories media and those who don't take lessons using scrapbook of child stories media.

The criteria for decision making for acceptance and rejection of Ho used a significance level of 0.05. If the significance value > 0.05 then Ho is accepted, but if the significance value < 0.05 then Ho is rejected. Table 5 presents results of hypothesis testing using independent sample test.

Tabel 5. Independent sample test

		Independent Samples Test									
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means							
		F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
										Lower	Upper
S C O R E	Equal variances assumed	.304	.584	-2.191	41	.034	-6.16848	2.81517	-11.85383	-4.8313	
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.209	40.968	.033	-6.16848	2.79217	-11.80752	-.52944	

Based on the results of the independent sample t test, it is known that the significance value in each class is <0.05 . The significance value in the control class and experimental class is 0.020. Thus, it can be seen that H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected. So it can be concluded that there is an effect of storytelling skills between students who take part in learning using scrapbook of child stories media and students who do not participate in learning using scrapbook of child stories media.

The choice scrapbook of child stories as a learning media because it contains stories, pictures, and interesting learning activities so that can be a stimulus for students to interest in storytelling learning. The use of attractive media can increase student learning activities so that it affects the results of students' storytelling skills, this is in line with the opinion that the use of media in learning makes it easier for students to learn and has an impact on the results of student abilities [13], [14], [24]. Scrapbook as a learning medium can provide material and information to students more easily, this is in accordance with research which states that varied learning provides experience for students so that it can provide more information received and good learning outcomes [25], [26]. The development of storytelling skills is directly proportional to their speaking ability [27].

The data analysis carried out, the scrapbook of child stories media had an influence on increasing the results of the storytelling skills of grade II elementary school students. The effect scrapbook of child stories for improving storytelling skills is in line with research which states that the use of media is effective for beginner children to be able to learn to tell stories [28]. The activity of compiling pictures contained in scrapbook of child stories s also provides learning experiences for students that have an impact on students' interest and the results of storytelling skills, this is in line with research which states that through pictures students will learn about concepts in composing so that they can become student facilities in learning [29].

Scrapbook of child stories media has an effect on improving students' storytelling skills. This is supported by the fact that story learning raises cognitive activities so that it will provide students with showing verbal skills and fun activities [8]. The scrapbook of child stories media makes storytelling learning more interesting and has an impact on the results of students' storytelling skills, this is in line with the research which states that the use of media in storytelling activities can be increased in terms of belief, mastery of story content, and the ability to express [16].

Thus, it can be concluded that using scrapbook of child stories on storytelling skills learning has more influence than storytelling skills of students without using scrapbook of child stories media. Selection and use of media appropriately will help students to learn more optimally. Therefore, as a facilitator a teacher should have the ability to select and use learning media to support the achievement of learning objectives. Finally, teachers in the learning activity should give students the opportunity to try their best. For example by providing good time management so students can focus and complete their work [30].

4. CONCLUSION

Through the results of hypothesis testing, it is known that there are differences in the results of the control and experimental class of students' storytelling skills. Based on this, it can be analyzed and interpreted that there is a significant influence using scrapbook of child stories media to improve the storytelling skills of grade II elementary school students.

REFERENCES

- [1] UNESCO, *Education for all global monitoring report*. United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2015.
- [2] Bulut, P., "The effect of primary school students' writing attitudes and writing self-efficacy beliefs on their summary writing achievement," *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 281-285, 2017.
- [3] Bahadorfar, M and Omidvar, R., "Technology in teaching speaking skill," *Acme International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 9-13, 2015.
- [4] Musfiroh, T., *Children's stories and developments (in Bahasa)*. Yogyakarta: Novila, 2005.
- [5] Bachri, B. S., *Development of storytelling activities in kindergarten (in Bahasa)*. Jakarta: Depdiknas, 2005.
- [6] Brewster, J. and Ellis, G., *The storytelling handbook for primary English language teachers*. British Council, 2014.
- [7] Julia, H. T., "Telling tales: Using storytelling to teach EFL kindergarten students in Taiwan," *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 13-25, 2015.
- [8] Bateman, A., Carr, M., Gunn, A., and Reese, E., "Literacy and narrative in the early years: Zooming in and zooming out," *Teaching and Learning Initiative*, 2017.
- [9] Phillips, L., "Retribution and rebellion: Children's meaning making of justice through storytelling," *International Journal of Early Childhood*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 2-14, 2012.
- [10] Serrat, O., *Storytelling in: Knowledge solution*. Singapore: Springer, 2017.
- [11] C. Nasir and N. Inayah, "Tell us Stories, Please! Storytelling for Young Learners of English," *Proceedings of the International Conference on the Roles of Parents in Shaping Children's Characters (ICECED)*, December 3-4, 2018.
- [12] President of the Republic of Indonesia, "RI Government Regulation Number 19, 2005, concerning the Second Amendment to Government Regulation Number 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards (in Bahasa), 2015.
- [13] Ge, Z.-G., "Does Mismatch Between Learning Media Preference and Received Learning Media Bring a Negative Impact on Academic performance? An experiment with E-learners," *Interactive Learning Environments*, pp. 1-17, 2019, doi: 10.1080/10494820.2019.1612449.
- [14] D. W. Saputri, *et al.*, "Integrating Game-based Interactive Media as Instructional Media: Students' Response," *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, vol. 12, no.4, pp. 638-643, 2018, doi: dx.doi.org/10.11591/edulearn.v12i4.8290.
- [15] Live, T. L. and Live, T. L., *Digital scrapbooking technology*,. Washington, D.C: Thomson Course Technology, 2005.
- [16] M. N. Hakim, *et al.*, "Hand Puppet: A Teaching – Learning Storytelling Media," *Getsempena English Education Journal (GEEJ)*, vol. 6. no. 2, pp. 182-190, Nov 2019.
- [17] Fikriah, "Using the Storytelling Technique to Improve English Speaking Skills of Primary School Students," *English Education Journal (EEJ)*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 87-10, 2016.
- [18] A. R. Syamsuddin and V. S. Damaianti, *Language education research method (in Bahasa)*. Bandung: Rosdakarya, 2009.
- [19] Johnson, R. K and Christensen, L., *Educational research: Quantitative, qualitative, and mixed approaches, fifth edition*. Washington, D. C: SAGE, 2014.
- [20] Taylor, J. M., May, J., and Reynolds, R., "Storytelling in 3D: Interrogating Engagement with Oral Storytelling in the School Classroom," *Storytelling, Self, Society*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 159-182, 2015.
- [21] Nurgiyantoro, B., *Assessment in Language and Literature Learning (in Bahasa)*. Yogyakarta: BPFE, 2001.
- [22] Patrick, W and Yannick, G., "The effectiveness of social media storytelling in strategic innovation communication: Narrative form matters," *International Journal of Strategic Communication*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 152-166, 2019.
- [23] Fink, S and Mackrodt, B., "Innovations- und technologie kommunikation: Vermittlung und positionierung komplexer themen," *Handbuch Unternehmenskommunikation (Corporate Communications Handbook)*. Wiesbaden, Germany: Springer, pp. 1285–1301, 2014
- [24] Aldilah, K and Nadya, N. N., "The effectiveness of storytelling and story reading methods in teaching speaking," *ETERNAL (English, Teaching, Learning, and Research Journal)*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 181-199, 2018.
- [25] Ebata, "Motivation Factors in language learning," *The Internet TESL Journal*, vol. 14, no. 4, 2008.
- [26] A. Lutfi, "Motivating students to learn science by applying bilingual comic learning media (in Bahasa)," *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran*, vol. 20, pp. 152-159, 2013.
- [27] Mukminatus, Z., "Storytelling to improve students' speaking skill English education," *Jurnal Tadris Bahasa Inggris*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 119-134, 2017.
- [28] Donoghue, M. R., *Language arts: Integrating skills for classroom teaching*. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2009.
- [29] M. I. J. Nazir, Aftab Haider Rizvi, and Ramachandra V. Pujeri, "Skill development in Multimedia Based Learning Environment in Higher Education: An Operational Model," *International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Research*, vol. 2, no. 11, pp. 820-828, 2012.
- [30] Fatma, A., "Perspectives of learners and teachers on implementing the storytelling strategy as a way to develop story writing skills among middle school students," *Cogent Education*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1-23, 2017.